

VIBRATIONS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS ON THE BASIS OF A UNIFIED FIVE-DEGREES-OF-FREEDOM THEORY

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ABSTRACT

Dealing with the free vibration problem of laminated circular cylindrical shells having a symmetric cross-ply lay-up, this paper is an application of the unified shell theory presented in Ref. [1]. For the problem considered, an appropriate, particular case of that shell theory [1] is presented and, for shells subjected to certain simply supported edge boundary conditions, the corresponding solution procedure is outlined. Numerical results based on different displacement and interlaminar stress distributions are presented and compared with corresponding results based on an exact three-dimensional solution.

1. INTRODUCTION

A theoretical unification of most of the variationally consistent, displacement based, classical and shear deformable cylindrical shell theories available in the literature has been presented in a recent paper [1]. This has been achieved by introducing into the shell displacement approximation certain general functions of the transverse coordinate which account for the incorporation of the transverse shear deformation effects. Avoiding to provide with a single choice of the forms of these "shear deformation shape functions" before or during the variational formulation of the general theory, the theoretical formulation presented in Ref. [1] left open possibilities for a multiple, *a-posteriori* specification of particular shear deformable shell theories. As a result, the classical Donnell-, Love- and Sanders-type shell theories [2], as well as their well known uniform [3-5] and parabolic [6-9] shear deformable analogues, were obtained as particular cases. Moreover, a generalized "zig-zag" displacement model presented in Ref. [1] gave further multiple freedom in achieving continuous distributions of interlaminar stresses through the thickness of an unsymmetric cross-ply laminated cylindrical shell.

Coming as a first application of the unified shell theory presented in Ref. [1], this paper deals with the free vibration problem of symmetric cross-ply laminated circular cylindrical shells, subjected to simply supported edge boundary conditions. For this problem, an appropriate particular case of the general theory presented in Ref. [1] is selected and the corresponding solution procedure is briefly outlined. Numerical results based on different displacement and interlaminar stress distributions are presented and compared with corresponding results based on an exact three-dimensional solution [10].

2. THEORY

Consider a circular cylindrical shell with a constant thickness h , and denote with R and L the radius and the axial length of its middle surface, respectively. The length parameters along the axial, circumferential and normal to the middle surface directions are denoted with x , s and

z, respectively, and are further considered as the coordinate parameters of a corresponding curvilinear co-ordinate system $Oxsz$. It is assumed that the shell is composed of an odd number, say $2N+1$, of specially orthotropic, linearly elastic layers which are perfectly bonded together and are arranged in the form of a symmetric cross-ply lay-up [11].

The present formulation is based on Love-type shell approximations and is an appropriately selected particular case of the general shear deformable shell theory presented in section 3 of Ref. [1]. In more detail, denoting with U_k , V_k and W_k ($k=0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N$) the displacement components of the k th layer, along the x , s and z directions, respectively, the theory starts with a displacement approximation of the form,

$$\begin{aligned} U_k(x, s, z; t) &= u_{0k} - zw_{,x} + f_1(z)u_{1k} \quad , \\ V_k(x, s, z; t) &= (1+z/R_k)v_{0k} - zw_{,s} + f_2(z)v_{1k} \quad , \\ W_k(x, s, z; t) &= w(x, s; t) \quad . \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, u_{0k} , u_{1k} , v_{0k} and v_{1k} are functions of x , s and t only and R_k denotes the middle surface radius of the k th layer. For a notation convenience, the middle-layer has been considered as the 0th shell layer ($R=R_0$), while the inner and the outer layers are considered as the $(-N)$ th and the N th shell layer, respectively. Moreover, $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ have dimensions of length [1] and for the present study, dealing with laminates of a symmetric material arrangement, they are assumed to be odd functions of the transverse coordinate, z . Imposing no further restrictions on the choice of those "shear deformation shape functions", an obvious multiple freedom has been introduced in the choice of through-thickness displacement distributions.

In section 3 of Ref. [1], the general case of shape functions which differ from layer to layer was considered. Here, for simplicity, $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ are considered independent of either the geometrical or the material properties of individual layers ($-h/2 < z < h/2$). Hence, in an even more special case in which,

$$\begin{aligned} u_{00} &= u_0(\pm k) \quad , \quad u_{10} = u_1(\pm k) \quad , \quad v_{00} = v_0(\pm k) \quad , \\ v_{10} &= v_1(\pm k) \quad , \quad R_0 = R_k = R \quad , \quad (k=1, 2, \dots, N) \quad , \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

the displacement approximation (1) yields a displacement form which is employed as a starting point for certain well known and extensively used shear deformable shell theories. In more detail, upon further choosing both $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ to be linear in z , the displacement approximation (1) would lead to a so-called uniform shear deformable shell theory [3-5], while a particular cubic choice would lead to a so-called parabolic shear deformable shell theory [6-9].

Similarly, different choices of those shape functions can be employed [12]. These [3-9,12], however, violate continuity of transverse shear stresses at the material interfaces of a laminated composite shell, while they would lead to corresponding shell theories that can be directly obtained as particular cases of the general formulation presented in section 2 of Ref. [1]. Hence, although in the numerical comparisons shown later, shell theories based on some of the displacement approximations employed in Refs. [3-9,12] are considered, the special case obtained on the basis of equations (2) is not considered in the present formulation. Here, independently of the choice of $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$, the displacement approximation (1) will result to a shell theory that is based on continuity of both displacements and interlaminar stresses at the material interfaces of the laminated composite shell considered.

To this end, it is denoted that equations (1) yield the following forms of the transverse shear stresses in the k th layer, ($k=0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N$):

$$\tau_{sz}^{(k)} = Q_{44}^{(k)} f_2'(z)v_{1k} \quad , \quad \tau_{xz}^{(k)} = Q_{55}^{(k)} f_1'(z)u_{1k} \quad , \tag{3}$$

where, $Q_{44}^{(k)}$ and $Q_{55}^{(k)}$ are the corresponding transverse shear stiffnesses [11] and a prime denotes differentiation with respect to z . Denoting next with z_k the k th material interface ($k=\pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm N$), a requirement for continuous interlaminar stresses on z_k yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{1k} &= A_k u_{01} , \quad v_{1k} = C_k v_{01} , \\
 A_k &= Q_{55}^{(0)}/Q_{55}^{(k)} , \quad C_k = Q_{44}^{(0)}/Q_{44}^{(k)} .
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Inserting next these expressions into equations (1), and requiring continuity of displacements on z_k ($k=\pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm N$) yields,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{0k} &= u_{00} + B_k u_{01} , \\
 v_{0k} &= D_k v_{00} + F_k v_{01} \approx v_{00} + F_k v_{01} .
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_k &= \sum_{i=\pm 1}^k (A_i \mp 1 - A_i) f_1(z_i) , \quad B_0 = 0 , \\
 D_k &= \frac{1+z_k/R_k \mp 1}{1+z_k/R_k} D_k \mp 1 , \quad D_0 = 1 , \\
 F_k &= D_k \sum_{i=\pm 1}^k (E_i/D_i) , \quad F_0 = 0 , \\
 E_k &= (1+z_k \mp 1/R_k)^{-1} (C_k \mp 1 - C_k) f_2(z_k) ,
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

and the upper or the lower signs appearing in \pm and \mp above correspond to positive or negative values of k , respectively.

Inserting finally equations (4) and (5) into equations (1) yields the shell displacement approximations in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U(x, s, z; t) &= u_{00} - zw_{,x} + [A_k f_1(z) + B_k] u_{01} , \\
 V(x, s, z; t) &\approx (1+z/R_0) v_{00} - zw_{,s} + [(1+z/R_k) F_k + C_k f_2(z)] v_{01} , \tag{7} \\
 W(x, s, z; t) &= w(x, s; t) .
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, independently of any *a-posteriori* specified pair of shape functions, $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$, a displacement approximation of the form (7) yields continuous displacements and transverse shear stresses throughout the laminated shell thickness.

Under the present considerations ($R=R_0$), a comparison of equations (7) with the displacement approximation employed in section 2 of Ref. [1] yields,

$$\varphi_1(z) = [A_k f_1(z) + B_k] , \quad \varphi_2(z) = (1+z/R_k) F_k + C_k f_2(z) . \tag{8}$$

Equations (8) relate the unified shell theory presented in section 2 of Ref [1] with the present displacement approximation which produces the following strain field,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \epsilon_x &= e_x^c + zk_x^c + \varphi_1(z) k_x^a , \quad \epsilon_s = e_s^c + zk_s^c + \varphi_2(z) k_s^a , \\
 \gamma_{xs} &= e_{xs}^c + zk_{xs}^c + \varphi_1(z) k_{xs1}^a + \varphi_2(z) k_{xs2}^a ,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\gamma_{sz} &= \varphi_2'(z) e_{sz}^a, \quad \gamma_{xz} = \varphi_1'(z) e_{xz}^a, \\
e_x^c &= u_{,x}, \quad e_s^c = v_{,s}, \quad e_{xs}^c = u_{,s} + v_{,x}, \\
k_x^c &= -w_{,xx}, \quad k_s^c = -w_{,ss} + v_{,s}/R, \quad k_{xs}^c = -2w_{,xs} + v_{,x}/R, \\
k_x^a &= u_{1,x}, \quad k_s^a = v_{1,s}, \quad k_{xs}^a = u_{1,s}, \quad k_{sx}^a = v_{1,x}, \\
(e_{xz}^a, e_{sz}^a) &= (u_1, v_1).
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where, for simplicity, u_{00} , v_{00} , u_{01} and v_{01} have been replaced by u , v , u_1 and v_1 , respectively.

The generalized force and moment resultants of the present theory are subsequently defined as follows [1]:

$$\begin{aligned}
(N_x^c, N_s^c, N_{xs}^c) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_x, \sigma_s, \tau_{xs}) dz, \\
(M_x^c, M_s^c, M_{xs}^c) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_x, \sigma_s, \tau_{xs}) z dz, \\
(Q_s^a, Q_x^a) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [\tau_{sz} \varphi_2'(z), \tau_{xz} \varphi_1'(z)] dz, \\
(M_x^a, M_s^a, M_{xs}^a, M_{sx}^a) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [\varphi_1 \sigma_x, \varphi_2 \sigma_s, \varphi_1 \tau_{xs}, \varphi_2 \tau_{xs}] dz,
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

and lead to the following constitutive equations,

$$\begin{aligned}
N^c &= A e, \quad (Q_s^a, Q_x^a) = (A_{44} v_1, A_{55} u_1), \\
\begin{bmatrix} M^c \\ M^a \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} D & D' \\ D' & D'' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k^c \\ k^a \end{bmatrix},
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where, A , D , D' and D'' are appropriate extentional and bending rigidity matrices, respectively. The elements of the column matrices N^c , M^c and M^a are consisted by the force and moment resultants defined by equations (10a), (10b) and (10d), respectively, while the elements of the column matrices e^c , k^c and k^a are consisted by the corresponding middle surface strains and changes of curvatures defined by equations (9d-f).

Finally, Hamilton's principle leads to the following equations of motion:

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{x,x}^c + N_{xs,s}^c &= I_1, \quad N_{s,s}^c + N_{xs,x}^c + [M_{s,s}^c + M_{xs,x}^c]/R = I_2, \\
-N_s^c/R + M_{x,xx}^c + 2M_{xs,xs}^c + M_{s,ss}^c &= I_3,
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$M_{x,x}^a + M_{xs,s}^a - Q_x^a = I_4, \quad M_{s,s}^a + M_{sx,x}^a - Q_s^a = I_5,$$

where, the inertia terms I_1, I_2, \dots, I_5 are obtained by adjusting appropriately the corresponding terms cited in Ref. [1] to the symmetric cross-ply lay-up considered in the present study.

3. VIBRATION SOLUTION FOR SIMPLY SUPPORTED SHELLS

Introduction of the constitutive equations (11) into the equations of motion (12) leads to the corresponding Navier-type governing equations. These can be brought into the standard differential eigenvalue form:

$$[L](\delta) = (0), \quad (\delta)^T = (u, v, w, R_0 u_1, R_0 v_1), \quad (13)$$

where $[L]$ is a 5×5 matrix of partial differential operators. Assuming that the shell considered is subjected to the following set of simply supported edge boundary conditions:

$$N_x^c = v = w = M_x = M_x^a = u_1 = 0, \quad (14)$$

at both edges $x=0, L$, the following solution form is applicable:

$$\begin{aligned} (u, R_0 u_1) &= (A, D) \cos(m\pi x/L) \sin(ns/R_0) \cos(\omega t), \\ (v, R_0 v_1) &= (B, E) \sin(m\pi x/L) \cos(ns/R_0) \cos(\omega t), \\ w &= C \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(ns/R_0) \cos(\omega t). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Here, m and n are the axial half-wave and the circumferential full-wave numbers, respectively, ω is the unknown frequency of vibration and A, B, C, D and E are unknown constant coefficients.

Inserting the displacement solution (15) into equations (13) yields a general algebraic eigenvalue problem of the form,

$$[T](\Delta) = (0), \quad (\Delta)^T = (A, B, C, D, E), \quad (16)$$

where the elements of the 5×5 matrix $[T]$ are generally obtained in terms of the unknown frequency, ω , and the geometrical and material properties of the cylindrical shell considered. The solution of such an algebraic eigenvalue problems can be obtained on the basis of a standard numerical procedure.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS, DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of the present formulation, in providing with reliable results for different choices of the shear deformation shape functions, is demonstrated in Table 1 on the basis of the prediction of the fundamental vibration frequencies of certain laminated shells having a symmetric cross-ply lay-up of the form $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. These laminates have the following material properties in all layers,

$$E_L/E_T = 25, \quad G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5, \quad G_{TT}/E_T = 0.2, \quad \nu_{LT} = \nu_{TT} = 0.25, \quad (17)$$

and were also used by Di Sciuva and Carrera for the numerical comparisons performed in Ref.

Table 1: Comparison of fundamental frequency parameters $\bar{\omega} = \omega L^2(\rho/E_T)^{1/2}/h$ of cross-ply laminated cylindrical shells with a $[0^0/90^0]$, lay-up ($m=1, n$ in superscripts) .

L/h	R/L	PRESENT WORK					Di Sciuva	3-DIM
		PAR _{ds}	HYP _{ds}	UNI _{cs}	PAR _{cs}	HYP _{cs}	ZIG-ZAG	EXACT
10	5	10.496	10.496	10.462	10.329	10.328	10.462	10.305 ⁷
	10	10.223	10.226	10.187	10.051	10.050	10.187	10.027 ¹¹
	20	10.099 ¹⁴	10.103 ¹⁴	10.063 ¹⁴	9.927	9.925	10.063 ¹⁴	9.902 ¹⁵
	50	10.032 ¹³	10.036 ¹³	9.996 ¹³	9.859 ¹³	9.858 ¹³	9.996 ⁸	9.834 ¹²
	100	10.013	10.018	9.977	9.840	9.839	9.971 ²	9.815 ¹
100	5	19.992	19.992	19.992	19.989	19.989	19.990	19.977 ¹⁸
	10	16.496	16.497	16.496	16.492	16.492	16.496	16.486 ²⁸
	20	14.777	14.777	14.776	14.772	14.772	14.776	14.752 ⁴³
	50	13.829	13.830	13.827	13.825	13.825	13.827 ⁷⁰	13.791 ⁷¹
	100	13.548	13.548	13.547	13.543	13.543	13.547 ¹⁰⁰	13.486 ⁹⁹

[14]. In more detail, for two different values of length to thickness ratio of such three-layered cylindrical shells, and for several values of the middle-surface radius to length ratio, the fundamental frequencies predicted on the basis of Di Sciuva's [13] zig-zag shell theory were tabulated in the second part of Table 1 in Ref. [14]. There they were further compared with corresponding predictions based on a classical (CST) and a uniform shear deformation (USDT or first-order) shell theory.

Those comparisons [14] showed that all results based on Di Sciuva's [13] theory were considerably lower than corresponding results based on CST. Moreover, they were relatively close but still lower than corresponding results based on USDT, for a 5/6 shear correction factor. In Ref. [14], however, no definite conclusions were made, with regard to which of the three theories compared was the most accurate. Nevertheless, Table 1 above reveals that corresponding results based on an exact three-dimensional analysis [10] are even lower. This makes therefore clear that, among the three shell theories tested in Ref. [14], Di Sciuva's [13] zig-zag theory provided with the most accurate frequency predictions.

Apart from the numerical results denoted as three-dimensional [10] or Di Sciuva zig-zag theory [14] results, Table 1 shows corresponding frequency predictions obtained on the basis of the present unified shell theory for several choices of the shear deformation shape functions. In more detail, all results denoted with a subscript "cs" (continuous interlaminar stresses) were based on the formulation described in section 2 above. These were obtained by choosing the shape functions $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ as follows:

$$\text{UNI}_{cs} : f_1(z) = f_2(z) = z ,$$

$$\text{PAR}_{cs} : f_1(z) = f_2(z) = z(1-4z^2/3h^2) , \quad (18)$$

$$\text{HYP}_{cs} : f_1(z) = f_2(z) = h \sinh(z/h) - z \cosh(\frac{z}{h}) .$$

The continuous interlaminar stresses obtained upon inserting the shape functions (18a) into equations (3) are distributed uniformly through the shell thickness. Hence, in a close connection with Di Sciuva's zig-zag theory [13], the choice (18a) cannot satisfy the zero shear traction boundary conditions imposed on the shell lateral surfaces. It can be similarly seen that the continuous interlaminar stresses based on the choice (18b) or (18c) are respectively distributed in a parabolic or a "hyperbolic cosine" manner through the shell thickness. Nevertheless, in either of these latter cases, transverse shear stresses take zero values on the lateral shell surfaces.

On the other hand, all results denoted with a subscript "ds" in Table 1 (discontinuous

interlaminar stresses) were based on corresponding displacement approximations that assume continuous transverse shear strain distributions through the shell thickness and, as a result, violate the continuity of interlaminar stress distributions at the shell material interfaces. These were obtained by setting both functions $\varphi_1(z)$ and $\varphi_2(z)$ appearing in equations (8) equal to the right-hand-side of equation (18b) or (18c) for a PAR_{ds} or a HYP_{ds} theory, respectively (see also Ref. [1]). It is of interest to notice that in the former case (PAR_{ds}) the resulting shell theory is equivalent to the so-called parabolic shear deformable shell theory presented in Ref. [9].

The superscript accompanying some of the numerical results presented in Table 1 indicates the circumferential wave number, n , for which the fundamental frequency shown was detected. In any case that corresponding three-dimensional and shell theory predictions were obtained for the same value of n , such a superscript is omitted from the corresponding shell theory result. It is of interest to notice that, for such thin and short shells, as the ones considered here (rings), and independently of the theory employed, neighbouring values of n result in slight or even imperceptible changes of the lowest frequency predictions.

Under these considerations, the following conclusions are made:

- (1) for the type of ring-shells considered in Table 1, all six two-dimensional shell theories employed provided with remarkably accurate results;
- (2) a couple of small differences observed between corresponding fundamental frequency predictions based on UNI_{cs} and Di Sciuva's zig-zag shell theory are considered as marginal;
- (3) these two latter theories are considered, therefore, practically equivalent in predicting the fundamental frequencies of the cylindrical shells considered in Table 1;
- (4) although PAR_{ds} and HYP_{ds} results are slightly worse than corresponding results based on UNI_{cs} and Di Sciuva's shell theories, corresponding fundamental frequency predictions based on PAR_{cs} and HYP_{cs} are practically equivalent and provided with the most accurate fundamental frequency predictions, and
- (5) despite that, HYP_{cs} results were always the closest to the corresponding exact, three-dimensional elasticity predictions.

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